

Grant agreement no. 312788

ORCID AND DATACITE
INTEROPERABILITY NETWORK

<http://odin-project.eu>

D2.3 First year communication report including results from first year event

WP2 – Communication

V1_5
Final

Abstract: This deliverable reports on the various external and internal communication-related activities undertaken in the first year of the ODIN project, including the first year codesprint and conference.

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	D2.3 First year communication report including results from first year event		
	WP2: Communication		Dissemination level: PU
	Authors: Gudmundur A. Thorisson (ORCID EU), Sünje Dallmeier-Tiessen, Patricia Herterich, Artemis Lavasa, and Laura Rueda (CERN)		Version: 1_5

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1. INTRODUCTION

The goal of the ODIN project is to identify and resolve issues relating to the ‘missing thin layer’ of persistent identifiers needed for a globally connected and interoperable scholarly communication e-infrastructure. The overall aim is to support development and stimulate adoption of interoperable identifiers for researchers, their inputs (cited work, data) and their outputs (publications and data), and to facilitate information flow within and between research communities, leading to greater re-use of data and innovative exploitation of the knowledge created.

A key component of ODIN’s strategy is engaging with and communicating project findings to the relevant communities. These and other communication-related project activities are managed by the Communication Work Package (WP2). The project Communication Plan, documented in a previous deliverable¹, lays out ODIN’s communications strategy.

In-person meetings are vital to the community engagement part of the ODIN strategy. The Kick-off meeting at the start of the project gathered important scientific inputs from selected external experts (see D2.2 Kick-off report). The First Year Conference and Codesprint and the Second Year end-of-project conference are likewise vital to disseminating project results to and soliciting feedback and validation from the broader community.

This deliverable reports on the First Year Codesprint and Conference, and summarizes other external and internal communication-related activities in the first year of the ODIN project.

2. EXTERNAL DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION

One of the key actions of the ODIN project is the public dissemination of its results and engagement with the key stakeholders in e-infrastructure and PID management. These actions comprise a continuous observation and participation in European and global developments on that matter.

To facilitate such a stable communication and intense feedback mechanism several

¹ D2.1 Kick off preparation, Communication plan and Website.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.154691>

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pillars for communication have been set in place during the first year.

The main tool for dissemination is the project website, where all the information is made available in a centralised place. In addition trusted repositories are used to enhance the visibility of the project output. The activities of the project have been announced and discussed via social media channels as well.

In addition scientific publications have been drafted and presented on major conferences. Furthermore, organisation of and participation in different events have been used to reach and engage with a wider community, i.e. the key stakeholder groups in e-infrastructure providers, publishers, libraries, data centres, research communities.

2.1 Project website

The ODIN website at <http://odin-project.eu>, hosted by ORCID EU, was launched shortly after the beginning of the project. Initially the site contained only basic high-level summary information on the ODIN project (mission, work plan summary, partners, events) and contact information. As the project progressed, a variety of other materials have been added, including a list of all published deliverables linked to documents published on Figshare as well as a project blog. The project members have been posting regular updates to the project blog, primarily news about public documents, deliverables and upcoming events.

Traffic to the website has grown steadily throughout the first year. In the months leading up to the First Year Event approximately 6,000-7,000 page views per week were recorded. A website traffic overview can be seen in **Figure 1**.

2.2 Social media

All website blog updates and other public project announcements were disseminated by ODIN partners to their respective communities via mailing lists and social media. Wherever possible, e-mail messages and tweets included a link back to the project website and helped to drive site traffic.

Particular emphasis was placed on email and Twitter dissemination in the months leading up to and during the First Year Codesprint and Conference, both to drive event registrations and to raise the overall profile of the event and the project. In particular, project members made a focused effort by tweeting during the First Year Conference itself, to supplement tweets from individual participants and other community members.

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Figure 1: Tweets during the First Year Event

As per usual practice on Twitter, all tweets were labelled with a common keyword or “hashtag” (**#odinproject**). This enabled both participants and others to aggregate and follow the tweets, creating a live conversation around the topic throughout the event.

2.3 Publications

During the first year ODIN partner ANDS published a paper submitted for the eResearch Australasia conference:

Identity Awareness: Toward an Invisible e-Infrastructure for Identifying Data and Authors. Amir Aryani, Adrian Burton (ANDS). Published Feb 2013 on Figshare. <http://dx.doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.155650>

An edited version of the text in D4.1 (Conceptual model of interoperability) has been submitted to the *International Journal of Knowledge and Learning* for inclusion in an

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upcoming special issue on persistent identifiers². The special issue will be published in early 2014.

CERN in collaboration with Simeon Warner from arXiv submitted a short paper to the 17th international conference on Theories and Practices in Digital Libraries (TPDL 2013) which was published in the conference proceedings:

Rueda, L., Dallmeier-Tiessen, S., Herterich, P., Carli, S., Mele, S., & Warner, S. (2013). Providing Meaningful Information in a Large Scale Digital Library—A Case Study. Proceedings of Research and Advanced Technology for Digital Libraries. Lecture Notes in Computer Science Volume 8092, 2013, pp 279-284. doi: 10.1007/978-3-642-40501-3_28

2.4 Presentations and participation at conferences

ODIN partners have been presenting project results regularly at various non-ODIN events of various types and audience sizes throughout the first year. These activities are summarized in **Annex D**.

2.5 Public deliverables

During the first year ODIN has made publicly available its deliverables, as planned. They have been published on the public archive Figshare under a CC-BY licence. In order to ease access and citation, all of them have a persistent DataCite DOI name assigned.

The project website lists the published deliverables on the “Project Outputs” page³, each with a DOI hyperlink to the document on Figshare. We decided to publish on Figshare instead of on the project website to ensure that these documents would be preserved and available online in the long term, beyond the lifetime of the website and the project itself. Figshare provides usage statistics for these documents, as of October 28, 2013 they have been viewed a combined 1,283 times (see per-document statistics on the Figshare website⁴).

² <http://www.inderscience.com/info/ingeneral/cfp.php?id=2202>

³ <http://odin-project.eu/project-outputs/>

⁴ http://figshare.com/authors/ODIN_Consortium/101695

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Audience Overview

Jan 15, 2013 - Oct 15, 2013

Figure 2: Audience Overview (Google Analytics)

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Figure 3: Distribution of the visitors (Google Analytics)

3. FIRST YEAR EVENT: CODESPRINT AND CONFERENCE

Public events are a crucial part of ODIN outreach activities. The first of the three main ODIN events was the Kick-off Meeting that took place in Berlin on October 18th 2012. A report from this meeting was published as deliverable D2.2 (Kick-off report). The first year conference and the Codesprint took place at CERN one year later (see chapter 3).

One year after the ODIN launch, a major ODIN community event was held at CERN, between October 15th and October 17th 2013. As outlined in the project Communication Plan, the First Year Event was a combination of a hands-on Codesprint (or Hackathon) and a traditional-style Conference in the Globe at CERN.

The Codesprint targeted the technical communities interested in building on the first year results of ODIN, in particular of the results of WP4. Their engagement resulted in several new features that were developed over the course of the 1.5days event.

The 1st year event engaged stakeholders beyond the technical layer, i.e. representatives from data centres, libraries, publishers and a diverse set of disciplines. ODIN project members presented the first results to the attendants to get feedback on the applicability and transferability of these results to other communities. The diverse set of invited speakers provided additional insights into the different perspectives and experiences of the individual stakeholder groups, which will be used for ODINs second year work plan.

3.1 First Year Codesprint, October 15th to 16th 2013

The main purpose of the Codesprint was to provide a venue for both ODIN participants and invited experts to work together on creating proof-of-principle software, which demonstrate the potential of the identifier “awareness layer”. The intention was to engage with stakeholders within and outside of ODIN and collaboratively explore capabilities, gaps and opportunities resulting from the emergent infrastructure.

It also served to stress test the proposed workflows and proofs of concept presented by the ODIN members. Positive feedback was received from the community, and the opportunity to validate through a hands-on application was very valuable for the project members.

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Figure 4: Part of the Codesprint participants visiting the CERN Computer Centre

Around 20 persons participated in the two days long event. Participants came from both ODIN partners and from external organizations not directly involved in ODIN. Among the external experts were Roy Boverhof (Server.biz) and Alejandra Gonzalez-Beltrán (University of Oxford), who won the best project competition at the ORCID Codefest held at Oxford on May 6th 2013 and consequently received funding from ODIN to attend this event.

Codesprint projects

After starting with a list of 12 potential project ideas (see **Figure 3**), the participants narrowed the list down to 4 projects based on the level of interest and the feasibility of completing the idea during the two days of the Codesprint. Groups of 3 to 5 members were organized to work in each of the project, with some participants collaborating between projects.

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Figure 5: First list of projects and initial votes

The list of selected projects was as follows:

- Embedding all my ORCID-claimed works (including data) on a webpage
- ODIN's HAMR - Human/Authority Metadata Reconciliation
- ORCID Union for data
- DataCite metadata form with ORCID lookup

The projects, further outlined in **Annex A**, were diverse in nature, ranging from building a set of tools that users can utilise to embed a list of their datasets and other ORCID-claimed works in their personal webpage, to analysing and cross-matching metadata content of ORCID and DataCite, in order to identify author-dataset links to push to a data centre. The code for all projects was posted to the Github code sharing website (<https://github.com>).

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The Codesprint results were presented at the First Year Conference on the following day. The session discussion underlined the importance of the results presented, as a hands-on example of the important developments carried during the year, which allowed obtaining practical results in short periods of time, such as during the Codesprint.

Codesprint outcomes

The Codesprint work produced several fully or partially working, rough software prototypes. Some or all of these will, with additional effort, be taken forward and refined to create useful tools and services in the future. Overall, the progress made by the Codesprint group is a testament to infrastructure approach taken by ORCID and DataCite - i.e. building open APIs and lowering the barrier for participation by developers – that proved useful and for tackling the outlined challenges.

Another especially valuable outcome of the Codesprint is having enabled key experts to be in close contact, working face-to-face together for two days. This action facilitated the building of long-term collaborative relationships between individuals and organizations.

3.2 First Year Conference, October 17th 2013

The purpose of the 1st year ODIN conference was to disseminate the project results after the first year, but also to obtain feedback and validation from the community on the work carried out so far. A total of 64 participants registered for the conference, of whom approximately half were from external organizations, not directly involved in ODIN. A full list of conference registrants is provided in **Annex B**.

The Conference lasted one full day, on the 17th of October 2013. The first part of the programme comprised an update from DataCite and ORCID and a summary of the first results from the project. The majority of the programme (see **Annex C**), however, was devoted to presentations from external speakers representing a diverse group of stakeholder organizations.

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Figure 6: First Year Conference, Laurel Haak's presenting ORCID

The conference is briefly summarized below. All presenters' slides are available via the event website⁵.

Conference summary, by session

The opening session featured **Adam Farquhar**, head of Digital Scholarship at British Library (BL) and president of DataCite, and **Laurel Haak**, Executive Director for ORCID, who reported on the latest developments in these two major persistent identifier infrastructure initiatives participating in ODIN. Adam presented the general guidelines of DataCite as an international association. The main strategic objectives for the period 2013-2016 were highlighted, together with the organization structure and the results from the past year. Laure presented the main reasons behind the creation of the ORCID initiative, supported by real examples of problems with author names disambiguation. The evolution of the initiative since its creation was explained, together with its international expansion.

⁵ <http://indico.cern.ch/event/odin-1st-year>

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Following the above, **Antonios Barbas**, Project Officer at the European Commission, presented (on behalf of Thierry Van der Pyl, the EC Director for "Excellence in Science") the strategy of the Commission for the upcoming HORIZON 2020 programme.

After a brief introduction to ODIN by **Jude England**, Head of Social Sciences at the British Library, representatives from each work package summarized the results of the first year of work and outlined their plans for the second year, set against the context of the four main ODIN challenges: interoperability, discovery, access and sustainability. ORCID's **Gudmundur Thorisson** reported on the early interoperability work in WP4, including lightweight software tools, which enable ORCID users to easily link metadata records in other persistent identifier systems (DataCite and ISNI) with their ORCID ID. **John Kaye** and **Sünje Dallmeier-Tiessen** reported on the proof-of-principle projects in humanities and social science (HSS) and high-energy physics (HEP) being undertaken in WP3 by the British Library and CERN respectively, which are the heart of the ODIN project. Finally, **Salvatore Mele**, Head of Open Access at CERN and Strategic Director for INSPIRE, highlighted the various issues and obstacles in discovery and accessibility caused by the lack of a widespread, open, interoperable, persistent identifier infrastructure, which the ODIN gap analysis and roadmap in WP5 aims to identify and address.

In the session "Complementary points of view" four invited external experts gave their perspective on the persistent identifier landscape and ODIN. **Paolo Bouquet** from the University of Trento and OKKAM offered a comparative look from the perspective of the DIGOIDUNA project, emphasizing on commonalities in objectives and methodology between the two projects, as ODIN builds on findings from DIGOIDUNA. **Eefke Smit** from the International Association of STM Publishers talked about the long-standing interest and investment in permanent identifier infrastructure in the STM domain, starting from the birth of CrossRef in the late 1990s, to the establishment of DataCite in 2009 and ORCID in 2012, over to on going pilot initiatives, like FundRef. **Tobias Weigel** from The German Climate Computing Centre (DKRZ) introduced the Research Data Alliance and underlined the importance of persistent identifiers at all stages of the research data lifecycle, not just at the final publishing stage. **Mark Hahnel**, founder of Figshare, closed the session by talking about the key role of DOIs in helping data published via the Figshare platform become citable and thus encouraging sharing.

The next session was titled "Experiences and challenges in disciplines beyond ODIN". **Susanna-Assunta Sansone**, Associate Director and principal investigator at the University of Oxford e-Research Centre, talked about the vital role of data standards in the life sciences and how identifying those standards and attributing those who create and maintain them is key to making shared research data reusable. **Sarah Callaghan** from the British Atmospheric Data Centre offered the perspective of the UK Natural Environment Research Council's network of six major data centres using DOIs in data citation, experimentation with data papers in overlay journals and peer-review of

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datasets. **Louise Corti**, Associate Director for the UK Data Service, provided a view from a service, which has a 45 year history of preserving and providing access to more than 6,000 valuable HSS datasets. UKDS have recently had good success with “impact stories” or qualitative case studies of research use of data in their collections.

Catherine Hardman, Deputy Director of the Archaeology Data Service, touched on many of the issues already mentioned concerning identifiers and data citation in the context of archaeology research, including “overlay” data papers and ADS’s efforts in assigning DOIs to the grey literature.

The final session featuring invited external experts was titled “Value-added services”.

Martin Fenner, Technical Lead for the Altmetrics project at PLOS, discussed the potential for alternative metrics for research data in helping with discovery and impact assessment, and in creating incentives that encourage data sharing. **Nigel Robinson**, Director of Operations for the York UK office of Thomson Reuters, introduced the Data Citation Index (DCI), a new service offered by TR which relies on persistent links from literature to data, in order to enable discovery of studies and published datasets in more than 900 repositories across all disciplines. The final contribution was from **Jan Dvořák**, EuroCRIS Board member and leader of the CERIF Task Group, who gave a historical overview of the CERIF specification for research information systems. As of 2012, CERIF supports persistent identifiers, so that DOIs and ORCIDs can be captured in and carried by CERIF-compliant metadata records.

After a Codesprint summary delivered by two extra-European ODIN members and participants in the Codesprint, **Simeon Warner** from Cornell’s arXiv and **Todd Vision** Director of the Dryad Digital Repository. ANDS’s **Amir Aryani** closed the conference with a set of concluding remarks on the day’s presentations. He asked the question “what do we need to do to make these existing/emerging infrastructures work together?” and, like several other speakers on the day, stressed the importance of building a culture of data citation.

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4. IMPACT

The ODIN project consortium represents a diverse set of stakeholders already. However, when discussing PIDs and their implementations it crucial that all disciplines and their e-infrastructure providers be part of the discussion. This is why ODIN is particularly concerned with outreach and engagement strategy. The impact of this strategy is presented below.

Engagement with key players, organisation of conferences and presentations at international conferences has resulted in a flow of updated information about the project and its feedback from the community. In order to track the level of impact and support the communication actions, the project has followed a number of websites covering ODIN, its mission and its events. A non-extensive list of references is included in **Annex E**.

Regarding the content, the sites referencing the project follow different patterns. There are many news pages reporting about ODIN public events (Kick-off, hackathons/codesprints or first year conference) and also about conferences where ODIN members attended. After such events, we can also find opinion blog posts concerning the arguments presented and comparing different initiatives. This coverage shows that such events and gatherings really are needed to trigger follow-up discussions. Furthermore, it shows how the community connects with and reflects on the project results.

We can also find both blog posts and entries on websites where ODIN members have been invited to participate to talk about the project results and ideas. Those collaborations opened discussion forums and are an important part of the engagement and dissemination strategy.

Finally, Twitter has proved to be a very useful and flexible tool for dissemination, particularly during conferences and to report news. We could find many cases of ODIN-related comments, suggestions and link exchanges, further spreading the project results.

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William Kilbride @WilliamKilbride

#CERN via the #ODIN project has #digitalpreservation codesprint fever for its conference this Oct: [http://indico.cern.ch/conferenceDisp](http://indico.cern.ch/conferenceDisplay.py?confId=238868)... #orcid #datacite

3 RETWEETS

12:36 PM - 14 ago 13

figshare @figshare

Tracking scientific output across the web: http://www.isgtw.org/feature/tracking-scientific-output-across-web#.UnJKd_Pwzv8.twitter ... #openresearch

1h

Trish Groves @trished

"@figshare: Tracking scientific output across web: http://www.isgtw.org/feature/tracking-scientific-output-across-web#.UnJKd_Pwzv8.twitter ... #openresearch" Thru ODIN = ORCID+DataCite Interoperability Network

1h

Ocultar conversación Responder Retwittear Favorito Más

Figure 7: Examples of tweets about the ODIN project results and events

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5. INTERNAL DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION

5.1 In-person meetings and conference calls

As per plan, the project partners have come together for face-to-face meetings approximately every 6 months, in order to follow the development of the project and share updated results.

The first general meeting, with participation from all partners, took place after the Kick-off Meeting in Berlin, in October 19th 2012. During the meeting, and after discussing the input from the public Kick-off event, the project members outlined the plans for the first year.

A second meeting took place at the British Library in London February 4th-5th 2013 where project partners shared the first steps taken and gathered information to continue developing the second half of the first year.

The third internal meeting took place at CERN, in June 25th 2013. This one-day short additional meeting was focused on the status of the first year deliverables and intended to help project partners to consolidate and share draft deliverables.

Finally, another general meeting was held after the First Year Conference at CERN, in October 18th 2013. As the one held after the Kick-off event, the project members discussed the input obtained from the public conference and outlined the further steps, outlining the second year of the project.

Several additional in-person meetings took place during the first year to support the development of the project:

- DataCite visited ORCID EU in Hannover in April 2013
- Dryad visited ORCID EU in Hannover in May 2013
- ANDS visited the British Library in May-June 2013
- arXiv visited CERN March 2013

Also, as per the original plan, representatives from all partners have met every two weeks via teleconference, with minor deviations (e.g. when dates coincided with face-to-face project meetings and holidays). The British Library as project coordinator

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	WP2: Communication Authors: Gudmundur A. Thorisson (ORCID EU), Sünje Dallmeier-Tiessen, Patricia Herterich, Artemis Lavasa, and Laura Rueda (CERN)	Dissemination level: PU Version: 1_5

produces the agenda and gathers and posts minutes from each teleconference to the project wiki. Extra teleconferences involving a subgroup of participants were scheduled as needed to discuss specific issues, such as final preparations for the First Year Codesprint and Conference.

5.2 Project intranet and mailing list

The closed, partners-only wiki site at <https://twiki.cern.ch/twiki/bin/view/ODIN/> (see **Figure 6**) has been used continuously throughout the first year to share notes from teleconferences, slides and other dissemination materials, draft conference agendas, draft deliverable texts, and more.

The screenshot shows the ODIN TWiki interface. The main content area is titled "Meetings" and is organized into three columns: "Phone Meetings", "Face-to-face Meetings", and "General Assembly Meetings".

- Phone Meetings:** A list of regular meetings from 02 Oct 2013 to 09 Jan 2013.
- Face-to-face Meetings:**
 - 15 - 18 Oct 2013 - First year and Codesprint (Geneva):** Includes links for Agenda, Practicalities, Participants, Random ideas, and a registration page.
 - 25 Jun 2013 - Deliverables Meeting (Geneva):** Includes links for Agenda, Practicalities, Participants, and Documents.
 - 04 - 05 Feb 2013 - WP3, WP4 and WP5 (London):** Includes links for Agenda, Practicalities, and Participants.
- General Assembly Meetings:** A single entry for 07 May 2013 with links for Agenda, Participants, and Minutes.

Figure 8: Internal TWiki, minutes

The closed mailing list odin-fp7-project@cern.ch is also used continuously as a forum for general, not moderated discussions among ODIN partners, as well as for posting announcements relating to the project.

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ANNEX A – FIRST YEAR CODESPRINT PROJECTS

The Codesprint participants created 4 software prototypes. After the Codesprint, the sourcecode, documentation and other resources for each project was posted to the Github code sharing website. Hyperlinks to the project code repositories are provided below.

Embedding all my ORCID-claimed works (including data) on a webpage

This project built on previous work by ORCID EU Labs to create a set of simple tools for ORCID users to easily embed a list of their claimed works in a personal web page. On the server side, the ORCID Feed service (<http://feed.labs.orcid-eu.org>), originally created by Martin Fenner, retrieves a list of works from the ORCID API and transforms into a feed of items in a variety of formats and citation styles. This tool was extended to support a companion client side JavaScript code which fetches a formatted citation feed and inserts into the user's web page as a bibliography. The user only needs to add one line of JavaScript and one line of CSS.

Server-side code: <https://github.com/ORCID-EU-Labs/orcid-feed>

Client-side code: <https://github.com/zimeon/orcid-feed-js>

ODIN's HAMR - Human/Authority Metadata Reconciliation

This project grew from the need for a data centre to add ORCID IDs for creators of works in their own system (and push this information DataCite) as researchers claim their works via the ORCID system. The example used for this project was the Dryad data repository, where less than 10 authors had included their ORCID in works metadata.

After applying a preliminary version of the HAMR analysis, almost 500 authors/creators were identified, covering more than 10% of all Dryad datasets:

- Total number of authors in Dryad: 15,491
- Number of authors who have claimed Dryad data in ORCID (so far): 9
- Number of claimed author-work links found by HAMR (includes both article and data): 496
- Number of data packages in Dryad covered: 441 out of 4,132 (10.7%)

Links to code on Github and notes: http://wiki.datadryad.org/ODIN_CodeSprint

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ORCID Union for data

A common challenge is integrating metadata describing persons and works stored in various unconnected systems or “silos”. The goal of this project was to enable person lookup in OKKAM’s Entity Name System (ENS) based on metadata harvested from DataCite and the ORCID public data dump. The tool can be used to “de-silo” links between an ORCID and a person’s works across multiple sources.

Code: <https://github.com/tjv/ODIN-Union>

DataCite metadata form with ORCID lookup

Looking up ORCID identifiers by name is a common requirement for ORCID integrators. This project implemented ORCID lookup for DataCite as an HTML form, using a widget that can be reused by others.

The form, based on previous work by Marcin Paluch for DataCite Canada, retrieves ORCID metadata for one or more creators for a work registered with a DOI in DataCite and generate metadata XML for the work. The ORCID lookup is done by a widget developed by ANDS that can be reused by others. The generated metadata XML conforms to the current DataCite Metadata schema and contains ORCID IDs and person names for the work. The metadata record can subsequently be used to update the DataCite Metadata Store (MDS).

Code and demo: <https://github.com/koelnconcert/datacite-metadata-generator>

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ANNEX B – FIRST YEAR CONFERENCE PARTICIPANT LIST

Name	Organization	Country
BOUQUET, Paolo	University of Trento, OKKAM	Italy
ARYANI, Amir	ANDS	Australia
ARYANI, Arian	IZKF Aachen	Germany
BARBAS, Antonios	European Commission	Belgium
BORTOLI, Stefano	OKKAM	Italy
BOVERHOF, Roy	Server.biz	Netherlands
BRASE, Jan	DataCite	Germany
BROWN, Josh	CERN	Switzerland
BURTON, Adrian	ANDS	Australia
CALLAGHAN, Sarah	British Atmospheric Data Centre	United Kingdom
CARLI, Samuele	CERN	Italy
CHEN, Xiaoli	Syracuse University	Switzerland
CORTI, Louise	UK Data Archive, University of Essex	United Kingdom
D'OVERSCHIE, Isabelle	Swets Information Services	Switzerland
DALLMEIER-TIESSEN, S.	CERN	Switzerland
DEMERANVILLE, Tom	British Library	United Kingdom
DVORAK, Jan	euroCRIS	Netherlands
ENGLAND, Jude	British Library	United Kingdom
FARQUHAR, Adam	British Library	United Kingdom
FENNER, Martin	ORCID EU	Germany
FRANKE, Michael	Max Planck Digital Library	Germany
GONZÁLEZ-BELTRÁN, A.	University of Oxford	United Kingdom
GUTKNECHT, Christian	University of Bern	Switzerland
HAAK, Laurel	ORCID	United States Of America
HAHNEL, Mark	Figshare	United Kingdom
HARDMAN, Catherine	Archaeology Data Service	United Kingdom
HEMMER, Frédéric	CERN	Switzerland
HERTERICH, Patricia	CERN	Switzerland
IVANOVA, Neli Zhivkova	University of Sofia (BG)	Switzerland
KALODIMAS, Nikolaos	CERN	Switzerland
KAYE, John	British Library	United Kingdom
KENALL, Amye	Biomed Central	United Kingdom

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KOUSIDIS, Konstantinos	CERN	Switzerland
KUNCAR, Jiri	CERN	Switzerland
LAVASA, Artemis	CERN	Switzerland
MELE, Salvatore	CERN	Switzerland
MOFFAT, Graeme	-	Switzerland
NAVAS,, Miguel	University of Barcelona	Spain
NEDKOV, Nedko	N. and K. University of Athens	Greece
NEUROTH, Heike	Göttingen State, University Library	Germany
NIETZOLD, Alexander	CERN	Norway
ODONI, Fabian	SII, HTW Chur	Switzerland
PETERS, Sebastian	DataCite	Germany
PURCELL, Andrew	CERN	Switzerland
ROBINSON, Nigel	Thomson Reuters	United Kingdom
RUEDA, Laura	CERN	Switzerland
RUIZ, Sergio	DataCite	United Kingdom
SANSONE, Susanna	University of Oxford	United Kingdom
SCHERLE, Ryan	Dryad Digital Repository	United States Of America
SCHNEIDER, René	Haute Ecole de Gestion	Switzerland
SENST, Henriette	Robert Koch-Institut	Germany
SMIT, Eefke	STM Association	Netherlands
SOE, Minn	King's College London	Switzerland
THORISSON, Gudmundur	ORCID	Iceland
VASILEV, Martin	CERN	France
VIGEN, Jens	CERN	Switzerland
VISION, Todd	Dryad Digital Repository	United States Of America
WARNER, Simeon	Cornell University Library, arXiv	United States Of America
WEIGEL, Tobias	DKRZ / University of Hamburg	Germany
WEIGERT, Verena	Jisc	United Kingdom

	D2.3 First year communication report including results from first year event		
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ANNEX C – FIRST YEAR CONFERENCE PROGRAMME

Update on latest developments from DataCite and ORCID

- **DataCite** - *Adam Farquhar, head of Digital Scholarship at the British Library*
- **Supporting eScience with Persistent Identifiers and Linking Infrastructure** – *Laure Haak, ORCID Executive Director*

The EU strategy on open science and e-infrastructures - *Antonios Barbas, EC Programme Officer*

First results from the ODIN project

- **Introduction to ODIN** – *Jude England, Head of Social Sciences at the British Library*
- **Interoperability: connecting identifiers** – *Gudmundur Thorisson, ORCID EU and University of Iceland Computing Services*
- **Discovery: Proof-of-Concept in the Humanities and Social Sciences** – *John Kaye, Lead Curator for Digital Social Science, British Library*
- **Discovery: Proof-of-Concept in High-Energy Physics** - *Sünje Dallmeier-Tiessen, CERN Scientific Service, Open Access Section.*
- **Access: towards an open, participative and interoperable PID infrastructure** – *Salvatore Mele, Head of Open Access at CERN and Strategic Director for INSPIRE*

Complementary points of view

- **The DIGOIDUNA report** – *Paolo Bouquet, University of Trento and OKKAM*
- **The role of PIDs in scholarly communication. A publisher's perspective** – *Eefke Smit, International Association of STM Publishers*
- **The working group on PID of the Research Data Alliance** – *Tobias Weigel, German Climate Computing Centre (DKRZ)*
- **The significance of persistent identifiers in Figshare** – *Mark Hahnel, Figshare founder*

Experiences and challenges in disciplines beyond ODIN

- **Data standards, sharing and publication in life sciences: landscape, challenges and exemplars** – *Susanna-Assunta Sansone, Associate Director and principal investigator at University of Oxford e-Research Centre*

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- **Credit where it's due: data citation and publication in the geosciences** – Sarah Callaghan, British Atmospheric Data Centre
- **Managing sensitive data and authorship in Humanities and Social Sciences** – Louise Corti, Associate Director for the UK Data Service
- **The Archaeology Data Service: data preservation and persistent identifiers in UK archaeology** – Catherine Hardman, Deputy Director of the Archaeology Data Service

Value-added services

- **New metrics for data** – Martin Fenner, Technical Lead for the Altmetrics project, Public Library of Science
- **Identifiers and the Data Citation Index** – Nigel Robinson, Director of Operations for the York UK office of Thomson Reuters
- **Towards CERIF 2.0: semantical web and metadata** – Jan Dvorak, EuroCRIS Board member and leader of the CERIF Task Group

ANNEX D – PRESENTATIONS AT OTHER CONFERENCES

Event title	Date	Partner	Location	Event type	Audience size
Cohort and Longitudinal Studies Enhancement Resource (CLOSER) Leadership Team	29/11/2012	BL	British Library, London, UK	project meeting	20
BL Scholarship and Collections Open House	24/1/2013	BL	British Library, London, UK	open house	70
Identity Awareness: Toward an Invisible e-Infrastructure for Identifying Data and Authors	28/10/2012	ANDS	Sydney, Australia	conference	150
3ª Conferencia sobre calidad de revistas de ciencias sociales y humanidades (CRECS 2013)	9/5/2013	DataCite	Sevilla, Spain	workshop	60
FESABID 2013: XIII Jornadas Españolas de Documentación	25/5/2013	DataCite	Toledo, Spain	workshop	40
DataONE User Group	7/7/2013	Dryad	Chapel Hill, NC, USA	workshop	50
17th International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries	22/9 to 26/9/2013	CERN	Velletta, Malta	conference	300
ORCID Outreach Meeting	23/5/2013	ORCID EU	Oxford, UK	conference	150
International Association for Social Science Information Services and Technology (IASSIST) 2013	29/5/2013	BL, ORCID EU	Cologne, Germany	conference	40
British Library DataCite Workshop no. 6: Research data metrics for impact and citation	14/6/2013	BI	London, UK	workshop	30
Association of Librarians in Social Sciences Summer Conference	30/7/2013	BL	London, UK	conference	60
DataCite summer meeting 2013	19/09/2013	BL	Washington DC, USA	conference	160
Max Planck PubMan Days	24/10/2013	DataCite	Munich, Germany	conference	40

ODIN is co-funded by the EC under the e-Infrastructures Activity of the FP7 Capacities Specific Programme.

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ANNEX E – ONLINE IMPACT TRACKING

ODIN members dissemination materials
Coffeehouse: New ORCID-integrated data citation tool https://coffeehouse.dataone.org/2013/06/18/new-orcid-integrated-data-citation-tool/
Research trends: Fixing authorship – towards a practical model of contributorship http://www.researchtrends.com/issue-31-november-2012/fixing-authorship-towards-a-practical-model-of-contributorship/
PLOS Blog: New DataCite / ORCID Integration Tool http://blogs.plos.org/mfenner/2013/05/18/new-datacite-orcid-integration-tool/
British Library blog: ODIN Project 1st Year Event @ CERN - http://britishlibrary.typepad.co.uk/socialscience/2013/08/odin-project-1st-year-event-cern-october-2013.html
ORCID Blog: Upcoming events, ODIN First Year Conference and Codesprint http://orcid.org/blog/2013/07/30/upcoming-orcid-events
INSPIRE-HEP Blog: Enabling data sharing, citation, and discovery http://blog.inspirehep.net/2013/10/enabling-data-sharing-citation-and.html
News and general information:
International Science Grid this Week: Tracking scientific output across the web http://www.isgtw.org/feature/tracking-scientific-output-across-web
OKKAM on its collaboration with ODIN (Italian): http://www.okkam.it/index.php/ricerca/ricerca-e-sviluppo
Social Science Space: ODIN Project 1st Year event @ CERN http://www.socialsciencespace.com/2013/09/odin-project-1st-year-event-cern/
Force 11: ODIN (ORCID and DataCite Interoperability Network) http://www.force11.org/node/4447
UK Data Service: ODIN First Year Conference http://ukdataservice.ac.uk/news-and-events/eventsitem/?id=3629
Digital Science: ODIN Codesprint and first year conference http://www.website.dsci.it/events/odin-codesprint-and-first-year-conference
Various Scoop.it! journals: New ORCID integrated data citation tool, FESABID 2013 ODIN: ORCID and DataCite Interoperability Network http://www.scoop.it/t/digital-research-tools/p/4004146879/new-orcid-integrated-data-citation-tool http://www.scoop.it/t/gestion-de-documentos/p/4003103919/fesabid-2013-odin-orcid-and-datacite-interoperability-network-sergio-ruiz
Registration agency for social and economic data: Connect DataCite with ORCID http://www.da-ra.de/en/news/newsdetail/2013/07/01/connect-datacite-with-orcid/
GrandIR: Evento inaugural del Proyecto ODIN (Spanish) http://www.grandir.com/es/noticias/430-evento-inaugural-del-proyecto-odin

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Blogs
BioMed Central blog: Reporting on ORCID...and a Call for Stories http://blogs.biomedcentral.com/bmcblog/2013/10/30/reporting-on-orcidand-a-call-for-stories/
Dee'tjes: Providing Meaningful Information in a Large Scale Digital Library, TPD2013 http://dymphie.com/2013/09/24/providing-meaningful-information-in-a-large-scale-digital-library-tpdl2013/
Laura's Dark Archive: Supporting Evolving Research Needs http://darkarchive.wordpress.com/2013/07/31/supporting-evolving-research-needs/
ThinkEPI: CRECS 2013, la cita anual con las revistas de ciencias sociales y humanidades (Spanish) http://www.thinkepi.net/crecs-2013-la-cita-anual-con-las-revistas-de-ciencias-sociales-y-humanidades
Library Intelligencer: Report of the October 2012 Kickoff Meeting of ODIN http://blogs.unimelb.edu.au/libraryintelligencer/2013/02/12/report-of-the-october-2012-kickoff-meeting-of-odin-now-available/
Natasha Simons blog: An eResearch journey to Antarctica and beyond http://natashajsimons.blogspot.ch/2012/10/an-eresearch-journey-to-antarctica-and.html
Partially-attended: EC consultation on Open Data - a report http://partiallyattended.com/2013/07/02/ec-open-data-consultation-report/
Ecobibl: TPD2013 Semantisch Web http://www.ecobibl.nl/2013/10/tpdl-2013-semantisch-web.html
Bluesyemre: ODIN (ORCID and DataCite Interoperability Network) http://bluesyemre.com/2013/05/23/odin-orcid-and-datacite-interoperability-network/